

On the adjuvanticity of hyaluronan: The case of a SARS-CoV-2 vaccine

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ABSTRACT

Vaccines based on mRNA have been fundamental in facing the COVID-19 pandemic, however, they still raise concerns about stability and long-term efficacy. Thus, protein-based vaccines remain valid options and hence the study of effective adjuvants is crucial. Here, we developed a COVID-19 vaccine based on the receptor-binding domain (RBD) of SARS-CoV-2 Spike protein, which is covalently conjugated to the natural polymer hyaluronan (HA) that acts as an immunological adjuvant.

Vaccination of K18-hACE2 mice with HA-RBD was well tolerated, and elicited high and sustained titres of RBD-binding antibodies and SARS-CoV-2-neutralizing antibodies, without the addition of other immunostimulatory compounds. Most importantly, HA-RBD vaccination conferred long-term protection to K18-hACE2 mice after challenge with SARS-CoV-2, also in the case of two consequent infections driven by different variants.

These findings demonstrate the efficacy of HA-based vaccination against COVID-19 disease, and support the promising use of HA as an efficient and well tolerated adjuvant.

1. Introduction

Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus-2 (SARS-CoV-2) was first isolated in December 2019 [1] and was subsequently indicated as the etiologic agent of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) [2], which spread worldwide and caused a pandemic that is still considered as a potential threat to the public health by the World Health Organization (WHO).

SARS-CoV-2 enters the host thanks to the high-affinity binding between the Spike (S) protein of the viral envelope and the angiotensin-converting enzyme-2 (ACE2) present on target cells [3]. The S protein is constituted of two subunits, S1 and S2, with the S1 subunit functionally binding to the receptor of the host cell and comprising an N-

terminal domain, and a receptor-binding domain (RBD) that facilitates viral attachment by directly interacting with ACE2 [4].

Among the different therapeutic and preventive approaches studied in these years to counteract the COVID-19 pandemic, the primary role of vaccination for disease prevention has clearly emerged. Indeed, twelve vaccines against SARS-CoV-2 have been granted emergency use by the WHO [5], and they mostly use the S protein or its RBD domain as antigen [6,7]. In this regard, due to its fundamental role in ACE2 recognition and consequent viral entry, RBD is the target for most neutralizing antibodies (nAbs) that arise after infection with SARS-CoV-2 or COVID-19 vaccination [8,9], and is therefore considered a strategic target for antiviral compounds and an optimal candidate for vaccine design [10–12].

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Although the most progressed and licensed SARS-CoV-2 vaccines rely on mRNA-based platforms [6,7], this relatively novel strategy still presents some issues that need to be overcome concerning heat stability, safety, and ability to ensure immunological memory. Thus, the protein-based vaccine approach is still intensively investigated in order to satisfy the urgency of developing new vaccines at an unprecedented rate and scale, which are capable not only of eliciting high titres of nAbs against SARS-CoV-2 but also of stimulating long-lasting immunological memory [13,14]. Nonetheless, due to the poor immunogenicity that characterizes protein antigens, the study of effective and safe adjuvants is fundamental in the development of new subunit vaccines. Indeed, adjuvants can increase the response to the vaccine in the general population, but they are particularly useful in individuals characterized by a reduced response due to age or pathological conditions. In particular, they improve the stimulation of the T cell response along with the antibody production, allowing dose sparing and simultaneously increasing protection time. Finally, they stimulate heterotypic responses against antigens that have a phylogenetic relationship with the vaccine antigen, which is particularly important in the case of SARS-CoV-2 due to its continuous mutation in new variants [15]. Despite adjuvants play a crucial role in protein-based vaccines, their presence may complicate the formulation process and lead to variability in vaccine effectiveness across different populations. Additionally, protein-based vaccines often require multiple doses to establish long-term immunity, which can hinder compliance and overall vaccination coverage. Furthermore, the manufacturing process for protein subunit vaccines can be complex and time-consuming, as it involves the careful selection and production of specific antigens able to elicit a strong immune response without causing disease. Regardless of these challenges, protein-based vaccines remain a critical component of public health strategies, particularly for individuals with compromised immune systems [16].

Historically, different types of molecules have been employed as adjuvants for human vaccines ranging from natural to synthetic, and they can be classified according to their physicochemical properties, origin, and mechanisms of action [17]. Among them, a large number of natural polysaccharides have been considered as attractive tools to be employed as vaccine adjuvants and immunomodulators [18]. Indeed, microorganism- or plant-derived polysaccharides such as dextran, zymosan, inulin, mannan or chitosan have been intensively studied as immunostimulatory compounds and were frequently employed as antigen carriers and vaccine delivery systems in association to other adjuvants [19–23]. In this regard, we recently reported that the natural polymer Hyaluronan (HA) acts as an efficient immunological adjuvant for protein-based vaccination strategies. Indeed, we demonstrated that HA-based conjugates are both efficient and very well tolerated since they did not induce any sign of inflammation at the injection site [24].

HA is a linear glycosaminoglycan composed of repeating D-glucuronic acid and N-acetyl-D-glucosamine units linked by β -1,3 alternated with β -1,4 glycosidic bonds. This natural polymer is ubiquitously present in the human extracellular matrix and can be found at different molecular sizes from high (HMW; >1000 kDa) to low molecular weight HA (LMW; <500 kDa) [25,26], and it is well known in medicine for its remarkable physicochemical features. In this regard, it is known that LMW HA fragments formed *in vivo* by either physiological or pathological processes are characterized by immunostimulatory, proinflammatory, and strong angiogenic properties [25]. Additionally, HA has an active role in both innate and adaptive immune responses, which is mediated by interactions with several specific receptors (HA receptor for endocytosis, HARE; HA receptor for its degradation and cell internalization, CD44; receptor for hyaluronate-mediated motility, RHAMM; lymphatic vessel endothelial hyaluronan receptor-1, LYVE-1) [27], and also with toll-like receptors (TLRs) [28]. In the interaction with TLRs, HA fragments behave as endogenous damage-associated molecular pattern molecules (DAMPs). In particular, HA is recognized by TLR2 and TLR4 receptors expressed by a wide range of immune cells, including dendritic cells (DCs), monocytes, natural killer cells, and neutrophils.

Furthermore, TLR2 represents also a costimulatory molecule in all activated T cells, including the memory subsets [29,30]. Consequently, although HA has complex and diversified roles *in vivo*, it seems possible to select a predominant HA feature by using a proper polymer molecular weight, as we have demonstrated by promoting its adjuvant role [24].

To investigate the potentiality of HA as a novel adjuvant for a protein-based vaccination approach against SARS-CoV-2, a HA-RBD conjugate was tested for reactogenicity, immunogenicity, and protective efficacy against lethal viral challenges in K18-hACE mice [31,32].

Overall, data demonstrate that HA-RBD can be regarded as a potential vaccine candidate against SARS-CoV-2 infection, due to its ability to stimulate the production of long-lasting RBD-specific nAbs, and to protect susceptible mice from the infection with different variants of the virus, without any sign of local or systemic toxicity.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study design

The study aimed to assess the safety and efficacy of a HA-conjugated protein vaccine against SARS-CoV-2 infection in K18-hACE mice. Recombinant RBD protein was produced and conjugated to HA to generate the bioconjugate, and the reactogenicity at the injection site was analysed through Haematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) and multiplex immunofluorescence (mIF) of tibialis anterior (TA) muscle in a blinded fashion. Humoral responses were assessed by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and microneutralization assays for RBD-specific IgGs and nAbs, respectively. Germinal centre B (GC B) cells in the lymph nodes (LNs) and long-lived plasma cells (LLPCs) in the bone marrow (BM) were evaluated by flow cytometry analysis. To assess vaccine efficacy, immunized mice were challenged with different SARS-CoV-2 variants, and disease progress and survival were evaluated. Viral load was determined by qPCR and focus forming assay at different timepoints after infection.

Animals were randomly assigned to the different experimental groups, and experiments were conducted according to the principles of the 3Rs (replacement, reduction, and refinement). Sample size and replicates are indicated in figure legends. During analysis, no individual data points were excluded under any circumstances.

2.2. Materials

HA with average molecular weight of 200 kDa was purchased from Contipro (Cat: 600–01-07; Dolní Dobruč, Czech Republic) and used for the conjugation with recombinant RBD (Cat: 230–30,162; RayBiotech, Norcross, GA, USA) to produce the bioconjugate HA-RBD. The same RBD was also employed in the other vaccine formulations, by mixing it with Quil-A® or AddaVax™, both from InvivoGen, (San Diego, CA, USA). Nuvaxovid (NVX-CoV2373) Novavax vaccine was used as a control protein-based vaccine.

FreeStyle™ 293-F cells (Cat: R79007, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) were cultured in FreeStyle™ 293 Expression Medium (Cat: 12338018, Gibco, Waltham, MA, USA) and maintained in a humidified incubator at 37 °C, 8 % CO₂, on a shaker rotating at 125 rpm (CO₂ Resistant Shaker, Cat: 88881102, Thermo Fisher Scientific). African green monkey kidney Vero E6 cells (Cat: CRL-1586, ATCC, Manassas, VA, USA) were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium High Glucose (DMEM; Cat: ECB7501L, EuroClone, Milan, Italy) supplemented with 10 % heat-inactivated foetal bovine serum (FBS; Cat: 10270–106, Gibco, Waltham, MA, USA), 1 % Penicillin/Streptomycin (Cat: ECB3001D, EuroClone), 1 % HEPES (Cat: ECM0180D, EuroClone) and 1 % Glutamine Stable 100× (Cat: ECB3004D, EuroClone), and maintained at 37 °C, 5 % CO₂. Hyaluronidase (HAase, Cat: H3506), Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS), bovine serum albumin (BSA), Triton X-100, Tween-20 and Tween-80 were all purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Saint Louis, MO, USA). HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies anti-

mouse IgG, IgG1 and IgG2c from Bethyl (Waltham, MA, USA) were used for ELISA, while OPD peroxidase substrate from Sigma-Aldrich and HCl from Carlo Erba were used to stop and develop the colorimetric reaction. For flow cytometry experiments, the following antibodies were purchased: rat anti-mouse BV510-B220 (clone: RA3-6B2), rat anti-mouse PE-TACI (clone: 8F10), BV421-CD138 (clone: 281-2), FITC-CD19 (clone: 1D3), PECy7-B220 (clone: RA3-6B2) and BV480-Ig kappa light chain (clone 187.1) from BD Biosciences (Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA); Alexa Fluor™ 488-GL7 (clone: GL7) from Biolegend (San Diego, CA, USA) and PE-Cy7-CD38 (clone: 90) from Thermo Fisher Scientific. Dead cell exclusion was performed using Fixable Viability Stain 780 (FVS780) from BD Biosciences. Immunohistochemical (IHC) experiments were carried out with a primary anti-SARS-CoV-2 N protein rabbit polyclonal antibody (Cat: 9099) from ProSci Incorporated (Poway, CA, USA) and an HRP-conjugated secondary anti-rabbit antibody (Cat: 31460) from Thermo Fisher Scientific. Immunofluorescence was carried out with rabbit anti-mouse Ly6G from Abcam (clone: EPR22909-135), rabbit anti-mouse CD11c from Cell Signaling Technology (clone: D1V9Y), rat anti-mouse F4/80 from Bio-Rad (clone Cl:A3-1), rat anti-mouse CD19 from, eBioscience, (Waltham, MA, USA; clone: 6OMP31) rat anti-mouse CD8a (clone: 4SM15) and rat anti-mouse CD4 (clone: 4SM95), both from Thermo Fisher Scientific. The HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies goat anti-rabbit and goat anti-rat were both from Vector Laboratories.

Staining of infected cells for the focus-forming assay was performed by means of SARS-CoV/SARS-CoV-2 Nucleocapsid monoclonal antibody from Sinobiological (Eschborn, Germany) and peroxidase-labelled goat anti-mouse antibodies from Jackson ImmunoResearch Lab (West Grove, PA, USA).

2.3. RBD production and purification

The recombinant RBD protein (Wuhan strain) was transiently expressed in Freestyle™ 293-F cells as described previously [33,34]. Briefly, cells were thawed and kept in Freestyle™ 293 Expression Medium (Cat: 12338018, Gibco) before being transfected with a solution composed of plasmid DNA, OptiMEM and polyethyleneimine agent. The plasmid codes for a recombinant RBD modified at the C-terminus with a 6-Histidine tag, and also carries the ampicillin resistance gene under the control of a CMV promoter (kindly provided by Prof. Giulia Pasqual, University of Padua). Seven days after transfection, the supernatant was collected by centrifugation at 4000 rpm (Megafuge™ 16, Thermo Fisher Scientific), at 4 °C and filtered in 0.22 µm filters, to be dialyzed at 4 °C in binding buffer (50 mM NaH₂PO₃ monohydrate, 300 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, NaOH pellets until pH reaches 8.0). Ni-NTA-matrix solution (Ni-NTA-Superflow, Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) was added to the dialyzed supernatant and kept in agitation overnight at 4 °C, then matrix and supernatant were collected and flowed through a Poly-Prep Chromatography column (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA). After washing with binding buffer, elution buffer was added (50 mM NaH₂PO₃ monohydrate, 300 mM NaCl, 250 mM imidazole, NaOH pellets until pH reaches 8.0), incubated for 10 min and let flow through to be collected in fractions. Each fraction underwent a denaturation step and an electrophoretic run on 10 % Mini-Protean TGX precast protein gel (Bio-Rad) stained with GelCode Blue Staining Reagent (Cat: 24590, Thermo Fisher Scientific), together with H₂O as negative control, commercial RBD (Cat: 230-30162, RayBiotech, Norcross, GA, USA) as positive control and the Protein Ladder DualColor (Cat: 1610374, Bio-Rad). Fractions with similar protein quantities were dialyzed together, quantified by Nano-drop One instrument (Cat: ND-ONE-W, Thermo Fisher Scientific), aliquoted and stored at -20 °C.

The recombinant protein was conjugated to the fluorophores Alexa Fluor® 647 and PE by means of Alexa Fluor® 647 Conjugation Kit (Fast) - Lightning-Link® (Cat: ab269823, Abcam, Cambridge, UK) and PE / R-Phycoerythrin Conjugation Kit (Fast) - Lightning-Link® (Cat: ab102918, Abcam), following manufacturer's instruction.

2.4. Synthesis and characterization of HA-RBD conjugates

The chemical conjugation of HA to the RBD N-terminus and the characterization of the bioconjugate were carried out as previously reported [24,35]. Briefly, HA-acetal (4.5 mg, 0.34 µmol; degree of acetal modification 3 % mol/mol) was synthesised from HA 200 kDa. RBD (1 mg, 33.9 nmol) and, after 1 h, NaBH₃CN (0.2 mg, 3.2 µmol) were added to the solution and the mixture was stirred at RT for 48 h. The unreacted HA aldehyde groups were quenched by adding 3 equiv. of glycine. The conjugate was purified and buffer exchanged to Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS) pH 7.4 through Protein Concentrators PES (Pierce™, Thermo Fisher Scientific).

The total protein content was determined by the average of the results obtained by bicinchoninic acid colorimetric assay and Abs 0.1 % at 280 nm. After an extensive dialysis, the purity of the product was checked by size exclusion chromatography (SEC) to ensure the elimination of unreacted protein. The reaction yield was 88 % (w/w). Finally, HA-RBD was tested for LPS contamination, as previously described [24]. The average size and size distribution were obtained by dynamic light scattering (DLS) using a Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Instrument Ltd., Worcestershire, UK). The sample was diluted 1:6 with PBS and filtered through 0.22 µm membrane with Costar® Spin-X® Centrifuge Tube Filters (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). For the transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis, the sample (25 µL) was placed on a 400-mesh holey carbon grid with copper support. After staining with 1 % uranyl acetate the sample was observed with a Tecnai G2 (FEI) transmission electron microscope operating at 100 kV. Images were captured with a Veleta (Olympus Soft Imaging System) digital camera.

2.5. HA and HA-RBD digestion by HPLC analysis

HPLC analysis was performed as previously described [24]. Briefly, HA and HA-RBD were incubated with HAase and digestion kinetics were analysed by SEC-HPLC on an analytical Yarra SEC-3000 column (150 × 7.8 mm, 290 Å, 3 µm; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA), eluted with PBS pH 7.4 at a flow-rate of 0.5 mL/min.

2.6. Animals

Six- to 8-week-old females and males from two different strains were used. BALB/c mice were obtained from Charles River Laboratories (Wilmington, MA, USA), while B6.Cg-Tg(K18-ACE2)2Prlmn/J transgenic mice were purchased from The Jackson Laboratory (Bar Harbor, ME, USA).

All mouse strains were bred in IOV-IRCCS Specific Pathogen Free animal facility. All the procedures regarding the experimental protocol and animal care were approved by the Italian Ministry of Health (Authorization n. 355/2021-PR), in conformity with institutional guidelines (D.L. 26/2014). All handling and procedures were performed in compliance with the European Community Directive 86/609 for the care and use of laboratory animals.

2.7. Preparation of vaccine formulations

For vaccine preparation, the bioconjugate HA-RBD was diluted in 5 % glucose solution. For the other formulations, the protein RBD (Cat: 230-30162, RayBiotech) was mixed or emulsified with Quil-A® or AddaVax™ according to the manufacturer's instructions. In all cases, the final working protein concentration was 10 µg per mouse.

2.8. Immunization protocols and serum collection

Mice were immunized with 10 µg of antigen plus adjuvant in final volumes of 20 µL by intramuscular (i.m.) injection into TA muscle. Nuvaxovid (NVX-CoV2373) Novavax vaccine was injected in a volume of 100 µL, corresponding to 1 µg of Spike protein. Animals were

vaccinated with two different immunization schedules: a primary injection on day 0 and two boosters on days 14 and 21, or only one booster on day 21. The corresponding sera were collected one week after every immunization and every month thereafter for up to 1 year. Blood samples were collected from the mandibular vein of mice anesthetized with isoflurane/oxygen and kept at 37 °C for 15 min. Samples were centrifuged at 4000 rpm (Cat: 5417R Refrigerated Centrifuge, Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany) for 10 min to allow phase separation and serum was retrieved and stored at -20 °C for further use.

2.9. Evaluation of the humoral immune response

The presence of antigen-specific antibodies in the serum of immunized mice was detected by ELISA, as previously described (19). Briefly, plates (Costar Assay Plate Half Area, Corning Inc., Corning, NY, USA) were pre-coated with 1 µg/mL of recombinant RBD; then, serial dilutions of mouse sera (from 1:50 to 1:3200) were added and incubated with HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies (anti-mouse IgG, IgG1 and IgG2c) OPD peroxidase substrate and 3 N HCl were used respectively to develop and stop the reaction. The optical density (ODs) was read in a Victor X4 microplate reader (PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA) at 490 nm. Data were plotted as endpoint titres that were determined as the reciprocal of the highest serum dilution yielding an OD above the assay cut-off. For serum samples with OD values below the blank, a titre of 25 was assigned and they were plotted below the limit of detection (LOD) that corresponds to the 1:50 dilution.

2.10. Detection of anti-SARS-CoV-2 neutralizing antibodies

Neutralizing antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 were titrated by an in-house SARS-CoV-2 microneutralization assay. Briefly, heat-inactivated serum samples were diluted in DMEM in a two-fold series starting from 1:20. Serum dilutions were incubated in a viral suspension containing 2000 TCID₅₀/mL of SARS-CoV-2 (lineage B.1 (Wuhan), lineage B.1.617.2 (Delta variant), lineage B.1.1.529 (Omicron variant)), isolated from nasal swabs of COVID-19 patients in Italy) for 1.5 h at 37 °C, 5 % CO₂. Virus-serum mixtures were subsequently inoculated onto sub-confluent monolayers of Vero E6 cells grown in 96-well microplates for 1.5 h at 37 °C, 5 % CO₂, followed by addition of fresh medium containing 6 % serum to cell culture. At 72 h post-infection, the presence of virus-induced cytopathic effect was assessed by microscopic observation and crystal violet staining. All neutralization tests were performed in duplicate. Neutralizing titres were defined as the reciprocal of the highest dilution of the serum that showed 50 % neutralization of cytopathic effect (half maximal inhibitory concentration, IC₅₀). Samples that presented a cytopathic effect lower than the assay cut-off were assigned a titre of 28 and plotted below the LOD, which corresponds to the 1:40 dilution.

2.11. Immunofluorescence of infected cell cultures

Vero E6 cells were seeded in 12-well plates containing microscope round glass slides in each well, and cultured to obtain 70 % confluence at the time of infection. Infection with SARS-CoV-2 Wuhan strain was performed in BSL-3 laboratory by inoculating the aforementioned cell cultures with 100 TCID₅₀/well of virus resuspended in serum-free DMEM; cultures were incubated for 1.5 h at 37 °C, 5 % CO₂, and replaced with fresh medium with 3 % FBS. Three days post-infection, medium was removed and each well washed twice with PBS, incubated for 30 min with a fixative solution (4 % formalin, 0.1 % Triton X-100) and washed other three times with PBS. Slides were first incubated with a blocking solution of 1 % bovine serum albumin (BSA) and 0.05 % Tween-20 in PBS for 1 h, washed three times, and then incubated overnight at 4 °C with a pool of sera obtained at day 30 post-priming from mice immunized with HA-RBD. As a negative control, sera from animals previously inoculated with HA-OVA [24] were used. Anti-Spike

antibody (Cell Signaling Technology, Cat: 52342) was employed as a positive control. The next day, slides were incubated 2 h with goat anti-Mouse IgG (H + L) Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor™ 546 (Cat: A-11003, Thermo Fisher Scientific), then counterstained with Spectral DAPI (Akoya Biosciences, Marlborough, MA, USA) for 7 min, and finally mounted using VECTASHIELD® HardSet™ Antifade Mounting Medium (Cat: H-1400-10, Vector Laboratories, Newark, CA, USA). Images were acquired at 40×, with oil immersion objective on an LSM 900 microscope (ZEISS) and analysed with the software ZEN 2 Blue Edition (ZEISS).

2.12. Detection of germinal centre B cells in the draining LNs

Single-cell suspensions of inguinal LNs were obtained from K18-hACE2 mice 7 and 14 days after immunization. Cell suspensions were resuspended in PBS 2 % FBS, blocked with antibodies against Fc-receptors (CD16/32, clone: 2.4G2), and stained with Fixable Viability Stain 780 (FVS780) for live/dead analysis and the following antibodies: rat anti-mouse BV510-B220, Alexa Fluor™ 488-GL7, PE-Cy7-CD38. For the identification of RBD⁺ cells among GC B cells, a PE-RBD probe was used, as described previously in this section. The data were acquired on a BD FACS LSR II cytometer and analysed using the FlowJo software (BD Biosciences).

2.13. Detection of long-lived plasma cells in the bone marrow

Single-cell suspensions of BM were obtained from BALB/c mice 15 months after immunization and from K18-hACE2 mice 2 and 8 months after vaccine administration. Cell suspensions were processed as previously described [24,36], and stained with Fixable Viability Stain 780 (FVS780) for live/dead analysis and the following antibodies: rat anti-mouse PE-TACI, BV421-CD138, FITC-CD19 and PECy7-B220. For the identification of RBD⁺ cells among Ig-secreting LLPCs, cell suspensions first underwent surface staining to be thereafter fixed and permeabilized (Cytofix/Cytoperm Kit, BD Biosciences), and stained intracellularly with rat anti-mouse BV480-Ig kappa light chain and Alexa Fluor™ 647-RBD, as described in Materials and Methods. Data were acquired on a BD FACS LSR II cytometer and analysed using the FlowJo software (BD Biosciences).

2.14. Viral challenge

K18-hACE2 mice were acclimatised in the Biosafety Level 3 (BSL-3) facility for 72 h prior to viral infection. Mice were infected through intranasal (i.n.) administration at different time points after the vaccination with 10 µL of different strains of SARS-CoV-2 virus diluted in DMEM, to reach the dose of 10⁵ plaque-forming units. The SARS-CoV-2 variants used were: Wuhan, Delta and Omicron. Physiological conditions of infected mice were monitored daily until sacrifice, and clinical signs (i.e. body weight, appearance, motility, and respiration) were scored as reported in Table S1. The cumulative score in clinical signs was used to evaluate disease severity. Mice were bled at different time points to evaluate the antibody response and the presence of nAbs. At the end of the observation period, or earlier in case of high pathological score or loss of 20 % of initial weight, animals were sacrificed and nasal turbinates, brain and lungs were collected for further analysis. The whole right lobe of the lung was fixed in 10 % buffered-formalin for histopathology, along with one half of the brain, while the left lobe, the other half of the brain and the nasal turbinates were stored at -80 °C for RNA extraction. All experiments with SARS-CoV-2 were performed in the BSL-3 laboratory of the animal facility at IOV-IRCCS.

2.15. Histopathology and immunohistochemistry of murine tissues

After tissue harvesting, samples were fixed in 10 % buffered-formalin, dehydrated through a graded series of ethanol, and

embedded in paraffin. Four μm -thick sections were examined after staining with H&E by a veterinary pathologist and by a board-certified veterinary pathologist. For TA muscle sections, the percentage of tissue affected, muscular inflammation, and muscular injury were evaluated as percentage of tissue involvement and scored blindly as follows: 0, no tissue involvement (no findings); 1, up to 25 % of involved tissue (mild); 2, up to 50 % of involved tissue (moderate); 3, up to 75 % of involved tissue (severe); 4, up to 100 % of involved tissue (massive). Finally, a total score per animal was obtained by combining cumulative scores of lesion types.

Immunohistochemical (IHC) examinations were also performed on 4 μm -thick lung sections mounted on polarised glass slides (TOMO, Matsunami Glass, Osaka, Japan). Heat-induced antigen retrieval was obtained with 0.01 M Sodium citrate buffer, pH 6.0 for 60 min, at 97 °C followed by blocking of nonspecific bindings with 5 % BSA. Primary anti-SARS-CoV-2 N protein rabbit polyclonal antibody was applied overnight at RT in a humidified chamber. Slides were then incubated with an HRP-conjugated secondary anti-rabbit antibody for 60 min at RT. 3,3'-diaminobenzidine peroxidase substrate detection kit (Cat: K3467, Agilent Technologies) was used to detect immunoreactivity, after endogenous peroxidase blocking (Cat: S2023, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Non-infected murine pulmonary tissues were used for negative controls. Intensity of signal was subjectively scored in different compartments (*i.e.* interstitium, alveolar epithelium, bronchiolar epithelium and blood vessels) as follows: 0, not detected; 1, mild/weak; 2, moderate; 3, strong. Finally, a total IHC cumulative score for each lung was obtained.

2.16. Multiplex immunofluorescence

The Tyramide Signal Amplification-based Opal method (Akoya Biosciences) was used for mIF staining on the Leica BOND RX automated immunostainer (Leica Biosystems, Wetzlar, Germany), as previously described [37]. Briefly, 4 μm -thick formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded muscle tissue sections were deparaffinised by baking over night at 56 °C, soaking in BOND Dewax Solution (Leica Biosystem) at 72 °C, and then rehydrating in ethanol. Heat-induced epitope retrieval (HIER) pretreatments were applied at 97 °C using BOND Epitope Retrieval Solutions ER1 or ER2 (Leica Biosystem). Tissue sections were blocked with Normal Goat Serum (Vector Laboratories) for 10 min before applying each primary antibody. Before proceeding with multiplex staining, a fluorescent singleplex was carried out for each biomarker to determine the optimal staining conditions and the order in which the primary antibodies would be applied in the multiplex protocol. Primary antibodies were added sequentially on the slides: rat anti-mouse F4/80, rabbit anti-mouse Ly6G, rat anti-mouse CD8a, rat anti-mouse CD4, rabbit anti-mouse CD11c, rat anti-mouse CD19. The HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies were incubated for 10 min. The TSA-conjugated Opal fluorophores (Akoya Biosciences) were then added for 10 min. Slides were rinsed with washing buffer after each step. Finally, the spectral DAPI (Akoya Biosciences) was used as nuclear counterstaining, and slides were mounted in ProLong Diamond Anti-fade Mountant (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

Multiplex stained slides were imaged using the Mantra Quantitative Pathology Workstation (Akoya Biosciences) at 20 \times magnification. The inForm Image Analysis software (version 2.4.9, Akoya Biosciences) was used to unmix multispectral images. A selection of representative multispectral images was used to train the inForm software to create algorithms to apply in the batch analysis of all acquired multispectral images. phenoptrReports (add-ins for R Studio from Akoya Biosciences) was used to calculate cell densities (number of cells/ mm^2).

2.17. qRT-PCR

Nucleic acids were isolated from 100 μL of clarified lung or brain homogenates, and 200 μL of clarified nasal turbinate homogenates, with

the MagMax Core Nucleic Acids Purification Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific) on a KingFisher instrument. qPCR was carried out with the AgPath-IDTM One-Step RT-PCR (Thermo Fisher Scientific), 30 nM of each primer (E_Sarbeco_F 5'-ACAGGTACGTTAATAGTTAATAGCGT-3'; E_Sarbeco_F 5'-ATATTGCAGCAGTACGCACACA-3'), 10 nM probe (E_Sarbeco_P1 FAM 5'-ACACTAGCCATCCTTACTGCGCTTCG-3' BHQ1/TAMRA), 5 μL template RNA and RNase-free water up to volume [38]. Runs were performed on a CFX 96 Deep well Real-Time PCR System, C1000 Touch (Bio-Rad), as follows: 50 °C for 30 min, 95 °C for 10 min, followed by 45 cycles at 95 °C for 15 s and 60 °C for 1 min. Ten-fold serial dilutions of a synthetic plasmid containing gene E sequence were processed along with each run to develop standard curves and assess viral load. qRT-PCR data were analysed with the Bio-Rad CFX Manager software (Version 3.1). Results were normalized by β -actin expression (primers: FWD 5'-CCATGAAGATCAAGATCATTGC-3'; REV 5'-AAGCACTTGCGGTGCAC-3'; probe FAM 5'-TCCACCTTCCAGCA-GATGTGGATCA-3' BHQ1).

2.18. Focus forming assay

Infectivity was assessed through a focus forming assay. Briefly, clarified homogenates were serially diluted and incubated on confluent monolayers of Vero E6 cells, in 96-well plates, for 1 h. After infection, the inoculum was removed and an overlay of MEM, 2 % FBS, penicillin (100 U/mL) and streptomycin (100 U/mL) and 0.8 % carboxy methyl cellulose was added. After 27 h, the overlay medium was removed and cells were fixed in 4 % buffered-formalin, for 30 min at 4 °C. Upon removal, cells were permeabilized by incubation with a 0.5 % Triton X-100 solution for 10 min. Immunostaining of infected cells was performed by incubation of the SARS-CoV/SARS-CoV-2 Nucleocapsid monoclonal antibody for 1 h, followed by 1-h incubation with peroxidase-labelled goat anti-mouse antibodies and a 7 min incubation with the KPL True Blue™ peroxidase substrate (Sera Care). Solution of 1 % BSA and 0.05 % Tween-80 in PBS was used for the preparation of working dilutions of immuno-reagents. After each antibody incubation, cells were washed 4 times through a 5 min incubation with a 0.05 % Tween-80 PBS solution. Focus forming units (FFU) were counted after acquisition of pictures at a high resolution on BioSpot (CTL Europe, Bonn, Germany).

2.19. Statistical analysis

The results were analysed for statistical significance by using multiple two-tailed Student's *t*-tests, log-rank (Mantel-Cox) test and one-way or two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) for comparisons among multiple groups, as specified in the figure legends (* $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$, **** $P < 0.0001$; $P > 0.05$ if not indicated). The data are reported as the means \pm standard deviations (SDs) unless otherwise noted. All statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism 9.0 software (GraphPad Software).

3. Results

3.1. RBD production and HA-RBD bioconjugate characterization

RBD protein was produced by transfection of 293-F cell line with a plasmid encoding the soluble form of RBD carrying a 6-Histidine tag at the C-terminal domain, and purified by means of immobilized-metal affinity chromatography. The purified protein was characterized by HPLC, quantified and evaluated for LPS absence. The HA-RBD was produced by conjugating RBD to 200 kDa MW HA-aldehyde (Figure S1A), as previously reported [24]. The resulting bioconjugate was analysed by SDS-PAGE and SEC-HPLC to ensure the elimination of unreacted protein (Figure S1B, C), and the formation of the conjugate. The selected method of HA conjugation involves a reductive alkylation of the N-terminal amino group of RBD by using NaCNBH_3 as a reducing

Fig. 1. Humoral immune responses elicited in mice by HA-RBD. **A** Schematic representation of the standard immunization schedule (prime + two boosters) carried out in BALB/c and K18-hACE2 mice. **B** Time course evaluation of RBD-specific IgGs titres in sera collected at day 14, 21 and 30 from BALB/c ($n = 5$) and K18-hACE2 ($n = 5$) mice immunized i.m. with HA-RBD, and K18-hACE2 mice immunized with either RBD alone ($n = 5$) or HA + RBD ($n = 5$). Data are reported as endpoint titres. **C** Schematic representation of K18-hACE2 mice immunization with the two-dose schedule (prime at day 0 and one booster at day 21). **D** Evaluation of RBD-specific total IgGs and IgG subclasses titres in sera collected at day 30 from K18-hACE2 mice ($n = 9$) immunized as in (C). Data are reported as endpoint titres. **E** Cumulative graph of nAbs detected in sera collected at day 30 from K18-hACE2 mice ($n = 20$) immunized as in (C). Each symbol refers to individual animals, while the solid and dashed lines representing the median value and quartiles, respectively.

agent, a well-known chemistry that has been widely exploited for preparing several polyethylene glycol-protein and HA-protein conjugates [39–41], some of which are currently in clinical use [42]. In particular, SDS-PAGE showed the purity of the recombinant RBD protein that migrates as an approximately 30 kDa protein band in reducing conditions (lane 1, Figure S1B); upon conjugation with HA, RBD migrates according to the characteristic of the polymer (lane 2, Figure S1B). SEC-HPLC analysis showed a peak of RBD that appeared at 9.38 min, whereas the elution profile of the HA-conjugated RBD showed a new peak at 5.1 min confirming the absence of unreacted protein (Figure S1C). At dynamic light scattering (DLS), the conjugate hydrodynamic volume was detected as 13.3 nm in accordance with previous investigations of other HA

bioconjugates (Table S2, [43]). The conjugate forms a transparent solution, and it is not a micro-/nanoparticles suspension. In fact, the transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis did not show any particles (Figure S1D). Additionally, SEC-HPLC analysis performed after *in vitro* incubation of HA-RBD with HAase (Figure S1E), showed that the enzyme digests the HA moiety of HA-RBD generating HA derivatives with MWs ranging from 3.9 to 103 kDa, which were similar to those detected after the digestion of the unconjugated HA polymer (Figure S1F).

3.2. HA-RBD elicits strong humoral immune responses with virus-neutralizing properties

To assess the immunogenicity of HA-RBD, mice immunization was carried out by i.m. inoculation of the conjugate according to different immunization schedules. The induction of humoral immune response was assessed over time by ELISA quantification of antigen-specific IgGs in mice sera. Results obtained from immunization of either BALB/c or K18-hACE2 transgenic mice showed a similar trend of RBD-specific IgGs production. In particular, in both BALB/c and K18-hACE2 mice vaccinated with the standard schedule (prime at day 0, first and second booster at day 14 and 21, respectively; Fig. 1A) RBD-specific IgGs were slightly detectable following the first bioconjugate injection, while progressively and strongly increased upon subsequent vaccine administrations. K18-hACE2 mice were also immunized with RBD alone or simply mixed with HA (HA + RBD). Notably, both experimental conditions induced detectable but negligible amounts of RBD-specific IgGs only after the third antigen dose, thus confirming that the chemical conjugation between HA and RBD is crucial for the induction of a robust humoral response (Fig. 1B).

On the other hand, as a two-dose schedule has been currently employed for all the vaccines against SARS-CoV-2 in clinical use, we were prompted to test whether a reduction from three to two doses (prime at day 0 and a single booster at day 21; Fig. 1C) could stimulate similar results. This approach was tested in the SARS-CoV-2-susceptible K18-hACE2 strain, and results showed that also this antigen dose-sparing schedule proved optimal in inducing RBD-specific IgGs (Fig. 1D). Additionally, evaluation of IgG subclasses revealed that RBD-specific IgGs elicited following two doses of the HA-RBD vaccine, were mainly constituted by IgG1, even though the IgG2c subclass was also well represented and detectable, a feature that suggests the induction also of the cellular arm of the immune response (Fig. 1D). Functionally, sera from immunized mice clearly detected SARS-CoV-2-infected Vero E6 cells *in vitro* (Figure S2), but more importantly proved highly efficient in neutralizing virus infection in susceptible cells, as indicated by the high IC_{50} titres registered in neutralizing assays (Fig. 1E).

3.3. HA-RBD performs better than the protein adjuvanted by commercial adjuvants, and does not induce inflammation at the injection site

The adjuvanticity of HA in the vaccine formulation was compared with the protein-based vaccine Nuvaxovid (Novavax) and the RBD protein administered with two well-known adjuvants. Quil-A is a component of the adjuvant Matrix-M™ employed in Nuvaxovid, while AddaVax was used as a surrogate of the MF59 licensed in several vaccines for human use. Two weeks after the first dose (day 14), only HA-RBD and Nuvaxovid were able to elicit a large amount of RBD-specific IgGs (Fig. 2A). After the booster, IgGs peaked in all groups with the Nuvaxovid-induced response being significantly higher. However, while the humoral response of Nuvaxovid-immunized mice significantly decreased over the following months, in the HA-RBD group the RBD-specific IgG titres remained stable.

As a surrogate of safety, we analysed the effects of HA-RBD at the site of inoculation in TA muscles by a double approach that consisted of the histological assessment of muscular inflammation/infiltration and injury, and the characterization of the infiltrating cell populations by

Fig. 2. HA-RBD outperforms the protein in commercial adjuvants and does not induce inflammation at the inoculation site. **A** Time course evaluation of RBD-specific IgGs detected over a period of 4 months in sera of mice immunized twice with RBD either conjugated to HA ($n = 6$), or mixed with AddaVax ($n = 9$) or Quil-A ($n = 18$), or with Nuvaxovid ($n = 12$). Data are reported as endpoint titres. **B-D** Muscle infiltration (B), inflammation (C) and injury (D) were evaluated as percentage of tissue involvement 24 h and 7 days after inoculation of HA-RBD, AddaVax+RBD, Quil-A + RBD and Nuvaxovid in TA muscles ($n = 3$ for each condition). Percentages were converted into a score as reported in the Materials and Methods section. **E** Total score per animal obtained by combining each single score. **F** Representative seven-colour multispectral images of TA muscles collected 24 h and 7 days after i.m. injection of HA-RBD, AddaVax+RBD, Quil-A + RBD or Nuvaxovid, scanned at $10\times$ magnification and cropped to show a smaller region of interest. The coloured legend in the bottom-right picture illustrates the markers used for staining, as reported in detail in the Materials and Methods section. **G-L** Quantification of F4/80+ (G), CD11c + (H), F4/80-LyG6+ (I), and CD4+ (L) cells density in TA muscles collected 24 h or 7 days after inoculation of HA-RBD, AddaVax+RBD, Quil-A + RBD and Nuvaxovid ($n = 3$ for each condition). Each symbol represents an individual mouse, and the bars indicate the means \pm SDs. Statistical significance was analysed using a two-way ANOVA test ($*P < 0.05$; $**P < 0.01$; $***P < 0.001$; $****P < 0.0001$; $P > 0.05$ if not indicated).

mIF. H&E staining of samples collected 24 h and 7 days after injection revealed that HA-RBD essentially did not induce lymphoplasmacytic infiltration, nor abnormalities or disarrangement of myofibers. Overall, no significant differences were detected in vaccine-injected muscles when compared to uninjected naive mice. Conversely, substantial tissue infiltration, inflammation and injury were observed in muscles injected with RBD adjuvanted with either AddaVax or Quil-A, and also with

Nuvaxovid albeit at a lower extent (Fig. 2B-E and Suppl. Fig. 3). mIF analysis fully supported such observations (Fig. 2F), and revealed that the cellular infiltrate in AddaVax+RBD and Quil-A + RBD muscles was essentially dominated by the presence of macrophages at both time points (F4/80+ cells; Fig. 2G). Dendritic cells (CD11c + cells; Fig. 2H), neutrophils (F4/80-Ly6G+ cells; Fig. 2I) and CD4+ T cells (Fig. 2L) were detected at low levels. The cellular infiltrate of Nuvaxovid-injected

Fig. 3. HA-RBD vaccination induces both a short-term germinal centre reaction and the production of antigen-specific LLPCs. A, B Percentage of overall (A) and RBD-specific (B) GC B cells as detected by flow cytometry in the inguinal LNs of naive ($n = 2$) and HA-RBD-injected ($n = 9$) K18-hACE2 mice collected between 7 and 14 days after a single immunization. Each symbol refers to a pool of mice and the bars indicate the means \pm SDs. C, D Time course evaluation of RBD-specific total IgGs detected over a period of 8 months in sera of K18-hACE2 mice immunized twice with HA-RBD ($n = 15$; C) and over a period of 15 months in sera of BALB/c mice receiving three doses of HA-RBD ($n = 7$; D). Data are reported as endpoint titres. E, F Percentage of overall LLPCs (E) and RBD-specific Ig-secreting LLPCs (F) detected by flow cytometry in the BM of K18-hACE2 mice 2 months ($n = 3$) and 6–8 months ($n = 6$) post-priming. G Correlation between circulating RBD-specific IgGs in the serum (1:50 dilution) and the percentage of LLPCs in the BM of HA-RBD immunized K18-hACE2 mice at sacrifice. H, I Percentage of overall LLPCs (H) and RBD-specific Ig-secreting cells among LLPCs (I) detected by flow cytometry in the BM of BALB/c mice 15 months post-priming ($n = 7$). L Correlation between circulating RBD-specific IgGs in the serum (1:50 dilution) and the percentage of LLPCs in the BM of HA-RBD immunized BALB/c mice at sacrifice. Each symbol refers to a mouse and the bars indicate the means \pm SDs. Statistical significance was analysed by multiple t -tests (A, B, E, F, H, I) and linear regression (G, L) ($^*P < 0.05$; $P > 0.05$ if not indicated).

muscles was essentially characterized by macrophages, and a significant accumulation of dendritic cells that were already present 24 h after injection to further increase by day 7. B lymphocytes (CD19+ cells) and CD8+ T cells were virtually absent in all conditions (2–3 cells/mm²; data not shown).

3.4. HA-RBD-induced antibody response is associated with both short-term germinal centre reaction and production of antigen-specific LLPCs

Mechanistically, the stimulation of antibody production by HA-RBD went along with the generation of RBD-specific GC B cells in the LNs of immunized mice, as observed in K18-hACE2 mice one or two weeks after priming (Fig. 3A, B and Figure S4A).

On the other hand, a long-term time course assessment of RBD-specific IgGs in sera collected from immunized K18-hACE2 mice showed that two doses of vaccine elicited a durable response that peaked one month after priming, but persisted at high levels for over 8 months (Fig. 3C). These data were quite reminiscent of what was observed in BALB/c mice receiving 3 doses of vaccine (Fig. 3D), thus further supporting the concept that a two-dose schedule of vaccination is sufficient to establish both a short and long-term humoral immunity. Since this latter depends on the establishment of antigen-specific LLPCs, we specifically searched for this population in the BM of vaccinated animals. In K18-hACE2 mice, LLPCs were not detectable two months after priming but considerably increased between 6 and 8 months after vaccination (Fig. 3E and Figure S4B). Although apparently not specific for RBD (Fig. 3F), the LLPCs present in the BM appeared overall proportional to the amount of circulating antigen-specific antibodies (Fig. 3G). In support, even more significant results were observed in BALB/c mice 15 months after immunization with HA-RBD (Fig. 3H-L). At that time point, HA-RBD vaccinated mice showed the presence of significantly higher amount of LLPCs, which were still able to secrete IgGs that were clearly RBD-specific and moderately correlated with the presence of RBD-specific IgGs in the blood stream of vaccinated animals.

3.5. HA-RBD confers full protection to K18-hACE2 mice against a lethal viral challenge with the homologous SARS-CoV-2 strain

As the RBD protein present in the bioconjugate derives from the ancestry Wuhan viral strain, a first challenge experiment was performed by i.n. administration of SARS-CoV-2 Wuhan strain to K18-hACE2 mice that had been vaccinated with either the protein alone, HA + RBD or HA-RBD according to the standard schedule (Fig. 4A), nine days after the last booster. As reported before, evaluation of the neutralizing activity of HA-RBD-induced antibodies at day 30 showed the production of good titres of nAbs. Interestingly, after infection, the amount of these latter significantly increased, especially when compared to all the other groups (Fig. 4B). Accordingly, HA-RBD fully protected all vaccinated mice from the lethal challenge with SARS-CoV-2, while mice vaccinated with RBD alone or HA + RBD succumbed to infection within 6–8 days from virus administration, similarly to not vaccinated mice. Indeed, while HA-RBD fully prevented the onset of symptoms, all the other groups showed a severe loss of weight and high clinical score detectable from day 5 after infection (Fig. 4C, D, E). Furthermore, the immunohistochemical analysis of the pulmonary parenchyma disclosed moderate to strong SARS-CoV-2 nucleocapsid protein (N) immuno-detection in not vaccinated mice, which was mainly localized in type II pneumocytes of the alveolar epithelium and interstitial macrophages and mononuclear cells (Fig. 4F). Differently, lungs from HA-RBD immunized mice did not evidence comparable signs of viral infection, as indicated by the virtual absence of SARS-CoV-2 N positive cells or occasionally by the presence of very few immunopositive cells morphologically consistent with interstitial macrophages (Fig. 4G).

3.6. HA-RBD vaccination confers full cross-protection to K18-hACE2 mice against a lethal viral challenge with heterologous SARS-CoV-2 strains

Based on the results obtained with the two-dose vaccination approach, subsequent *in vivo* viral challenges were conducted using this schedule. In particular, we decided to reproduce the evolution of the human pandemic that was characterized by the emergence of different SARS-CoV-2 variants, while the worldwide massive campaign of vaccination had been carried out for a long time with vaccines derived from the ancestry Wuhan strain. Thus, we tested whether HA-RBD could confer cross-protection against challenges with different variants of concern, and compared these results with other vaccines. To this end, K18-hACE2 mice vaccinated with two doses of either HA-RBD, Quil-A + RBD or Nuvaxovid were infected with SARS-CoV-2 Delta strain (Fig. 5A). Titres of anti-Delta nAbs at the completion of the vaccination schedule appeared lower than those detected for the Wuhan strain, with the exception of Nuvaxovid group (Fig. 5B, C). Notwithstanding, HA-RBD-vaccinated animals fully survived a lethal challenge with the heterologous virus similarly to Nuvaxovid-immunized mice (Fig. 5D), thus indicating the induction of a sufficient cross-protective activity. Indeed, both the HA-RBD and Nuvaxovid groups did not display weight loss or clinical signs during the first 2 weeks p.i. (Fig. 5E, F). Interestingly, in the Quil-A + RBD group the titres of nAbs against both Wuhan and Delta virus strains only partially correlated with survival, since half of the mice succumbed to the challenge.

Next, we decided to mimic a common pattern of infection in humans, which is characterized by the re-infection of individuals with the Omicron variant of the virus notwithstanding they had already encountered the Delta strain. Thus, HA-RBD mice that had survived the Delta virus challenge for over five months, were re-challenged with the Omicron strain (Fig. 5A). Because Omicron is known to induce a milder response than other variants and remains mainly localized in the upper airways, being additionally not lethal in K18-hACE2 mice (data not shown), animals were sacrificed 4 days p.i. and the presence of viral particles was evaluated in the nasal turbinates by qRT-PCR. Results disclosed virtually no sign of SARS-CoV-2 genomic RNA, while this latter could be easily identified in not vaccinated and Omicron-infected mice (Fig. 5G). Noteworthy, analysis of the nAbs revealed that just one out of the five HA-RBD immunized mice evidenced a detectable and specific neutralizing activity against the Omicron variant, despite the presence of high levels of Wuhan and Delta nAbs in all animals (Fig. 5H-L).

3.7. HA-RBD confers long-term protection against COVID-19 disease

A critical issue in COVID-19 disease, and in general in vaccination, is represented by the capacity of approved vaccines to elicit long-term protection without the need for recurrent boosters.

To assess this issue, we decided to carry out an additional experiment where vaccinated animals were challenged with the virus several months after priming. Thus, a large pool of mice receiving two doses of HA-RBD was administered i.n. 8 months later with SARS-CoV-2 Delta strain. Thereafter, groups of animals were sacrificed at different time points after challenge to allow a time course evaluation of the response to the infection (Fig. 6A), or maintained under observation for survival. Before the challenge, mice still revealed variable but detectable levels of RBD-specific IgGs (Fig. 6B) that well correlated with nAbs against Wuhan strain (Fig. 6C, D). On the other hand, the neutralizing activity appeared quite reduced against Delta strain (Fig. 6E). Upon challenge, RBD-specific IgGs and nAbs remained essentially stable during the first week to strongly increase by day 14, a picture that was observed for both Wuhan and Delta strains (Fig. 6D, E). The pre-challenge immunity strongly impacted on viral replication. Indeed, time course evaluation of SARS-CoV-2 genomic RNA (Fig. 6F-H) and infectious virus (Fig. 6I-M) in different sites of unvaccinated and infected mice, revealed that the virus was present at high titres in nasal turbinates and barely detectable in lungs and brain at day 4, a picture that dramatically changed by day 6

Fig. 4. HA-RBD fully protects K18-hACE2 mice against a lethal viral challenge with the homologous SARS-CoV-2 strain. **A** Schematic representation of the experimental protocol in K18-hACE2 mice receiving three doses of either the protein alone, HA simply mixed with RBD or HA-RBD, and viral challenge ($n = 5$). **B** nAb titres against SARS-CoV-2 Wuhan strain detected in sera from naive ($n = 5$) and immunized mice ($n = 5$) collected at day 30 post-priming and at sacrifice (after infection). LOD: limit of detection. Points represented below the LOD corresponds to values below the assay cut-off. **C** Kaplan-Meier survival curves of naive and vaccine-injected mice upon infection with SARS-CoV-2 Wuhan strain. **D**, **E** Time course evaluation of weight changes (**D**) and clinical scores (**E**) in mice after virus infection. **F** SARS-CoV-2 N protein evaluated by IHC and scored subjectively in different histological compartments of the lungs from naive and HA-RBD-injected K18-hACE2 mice; lungs were collected at sacrifice (days 6 and 14 post-infection, respectively). **G** Representative IHC images of SARS-CoV-2 N protein in lungs from naive (upper panel) and HA-RBD-injected (lower panel) K18-hACE2 mice collected at sacrifice (days 6 and 14 post-infection, respectively). 20 \times magnification. In all graphs of the figure, each symbol refers to an individual mouse and the bars indicate the means \pm SDs. Statistical significance was analysed by multiple t -tests (**B**), log-rank (Mantel-Cox) test (**C**) and two-way ANOVA (**D**) (** $P < 0.01$; $P > 0.05$ if not indicated).

Fig. 5. HA-RBD fully cross-protects K18-hACE2 mice against a viral challenge with heterologous SARS-CoV-2 strains. **A** Schematic representation of the experimental protocol in K18-hACE2 mice receiving two doses of HA-RBD and viral challenge with SARS-CoV-2 Delta variant at day 35 post-priming. Mice surviving the first challenge were re-challenged with SARS-CoV-2 Omicron variant 150 days after the first infection. **B**, **C** nAb titres detected in sera from naive animals and mice immunized with either HA-RBD, Quil-A + RBD or Nuvaxovid ($n = 6$ for each condition); sera were collected at day 30 post-priming (before infection), and at the moment of sacrifice (after infection), and measured against Wuhan (**B**) and Delta (**C**) variants. LOD: limit of detection. Points represented below the LOD corresponds to values below the assay cut-off. **D**, **E** Time course evaluation of weight changes (**D**) and clinical scores (**E**) in mice after virus infection. **F** Kaplan-Meier survival curves of naive and vaccinated mice ($n = 6$ for each condition) upon infection with SARS-CoV-2 Delta strain. **G** qRT-PCR analysis of SARS-CoV-2 E protein gene in nasal turbinates of naive ($n = 5$) and immunized ($n = 5$) mice collected 4 days after re-challenge with the Omicron variant. **H**-**L** nAb titres in sera from naive ($n = 5$) and immunized ($n = 5$) mice collected at day 4 post re-challenge, and tested against Wuhan (**H**), Delta (**I**) and Omicron (**L**) variants. In all graphs of the figure, each symbol refers to an individual mouse and the bars indicate the means \pm SDs. Statistical significance was analysed by two-way ANOVA (**B**, **C**), log-rank (Mantel-Cox) test (**F**) and multiple t -tests (**G**-**L**) (* $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$; **** $P < 0.0001$; $P > 0.05$ if not indicated).

(caption on next page)

Fig. 6. HA-RBD confers long-term protection against COVID-19. A Schematic representation of the experimental protocol in K18-hACE2 undergoing immunization and viral challenge with SARS-CoV-2 Delta strain 8 months after priming. B Time course evaluation of RBD-specific total IgGs in sera of immunized mice ($n = 14$) just before and after challenge. Data are expressed as the ODs at 490 nm of the 1:50 serum dilution. Each line represents an individual mouse. C Correlation analysis between RBD-specific IgGs and nAbs against the Wuhan variant in the sera of immunized mice immediately before the virus challenge (day 240 post-priming). Data are expressed as \log_{10} of both ODs at 490 nm and IC_{50} . D, E Time course evaluation of nAbs detected in sera from naive ($n = 13$) and immunized ($n = 14$) mice collected just before infection (day 240 post-priming) and 4, 6 and 14 days post-infection, and tested against both Wuhan (D) and Delta (E) variants. LOD: limit of detection. Points represented below the LOD corresponds to values below the assay cut-off. F-M qRT-PCR analysis of SARS-CoV-2 genomic RNA (F-H) and viral titres (I-M) in nasal turbinates (F, I), lungs (G, L), and brain (H, M) from mice tested 4 ($n = 6$ naive; $n = 5$ HA-RBD) and 6 ($n = 7$ naive; $n = 4$ HA-RBD) days after infection. N Kaplan-Meier survival curves of naive ($n = 6$) and immunized ($n = 5$) mice upon infection with Delta variant of SARS-CoV-2. In all graphs of the figure, each symbol refers to an individual mouse and the bars indicate the means \pm SDs. Statistical significance was analysed by linear regression (C), two-way ANOVA (D-M), and log-rank (Mantel-Cox) test (N) (* $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; **** $P < 0.0001$; $P > 0.05$ if not indicated).

when viral RNA and infectious particles appeared strongly reduced in the upper airways but highly represented in lungs and brain. Compared to unvaccinated animals, HA-RBD-vaccinated mice showed lower viral load in essentially all the tested sites (Fig. 6F-M). Moreover, the three mice that survived 14 days p.i. had undetectable viral RNA in all the tested organs (data not shown).

HA-RBD immunization conferred long-term protection against COVID-19 disease and prevented weight loss and the onset of pathological signs in three out of the five vaccinated mice (Figure 5A, B), ultimately leading to significantly increased survival (Fig. 6N). Of note, the detection of viral RNA in nasal turbinates and lungs of HA-RBD-vaccinated mice inversely correlated with survival (Figure 5C, D).

4. Discussion

The COVID-19 pandemic has clearly underlined the importance of developing new and effective vaccines, ultimately leading to the clinical approval of mRNA vaccines. Even though the mRNA platform provides many advantages, the wide vaccination program has also evidenced some flaws such as side effects (e.g. anaphylaxis), the uncertainty surrounding the long-term protection, and not less importantly, storage and transport issues for unstable vaccines [44,45]. For these reasons, subunit vaccines still constitute a solid alternative. Although purified protein antigens alone normally elicit modest antibodies with little or no T-cell reactivity, the addition of an adjuvant in the formulation can lead to the induction of efficient and long-lasting immune responses.

Here, we report that a protein vaccination platform based on RBD conjugation to HA, a non-toxic and biocompatible natural polymer endowed with inherent adjuvant activity, is non-reactogenic, highly immunogenic and confers full protection against SARS-CoV-2 infection. More specifically, in both BALB/c and K18-hACE2 transgenic mice HA-RBD vaccination proved optimal in eliciting high and antigen-specific humoral responses also with a two-dose schedule, thus mirroring current real-world practice with all the approved vaccines against SARS-CoV-2; this allows dose sparing and increases patient compliance [15]. Moreover, HA adjuvant activity proved competitive in terms of efficacy over the two well-known adjuvants Quil-A and AddaVax, and was comparable to the optimized Nuvaxovid protein vaccine that has already reached the clinical application.

During the vaccination campaign connected with the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, vaccines have often raised concerns about safety and side effects [46], general features usually related to the adjuvants present in the formulations. In this regard, HA-RBD vaccine does not induce inflammation nor cause muscle injury at the site of injection, thus confirming previous results obtained with the model antigen ovalbumin [24] and supporting the concept that the mechanism of action does not rely on triggering local inflammatory reactions [47].

Several other works have already demonstrated how the RBD portion in subunit vaccine candidates elicits high titres of nAbs [48,49], even higher than the proportion induced by full-length S protein [50,51]. Notably, HA-RBD vaccinated mice produced Abs that disclosed *in vitro* neutralizing activity not only against the wild type virus but were also cross-neutralizing against Delta and Omicron variants, albeit at a lower extent. This result is particularly encouraging, since nAbs are

fundamental to confer sterilizing immunity but also to minimize the risk of antibody-dependent enhancement (ADE), which is always a matter of concern during the process of vaccine development [52,53]. The HA-RBD-induced nAbs proved their clinical relevance in the K18-hACE2 mouse model of COVID-19 disease [54]. In particular, the survival of all the HA-RBD immunized mice, together with the absence of clinical signs and viral protein transcripts in the lungs, correlated with the presence of Igs endowed with neutralizing activity, thus providing strong direct evidence that nAbs activity detected *in vitro* correlated with *in vivo* protection against viral infection.

The COVID-19 pandemic has been characterized by the emergence of different variants of concern, with many of them displaying the ability to partially escape neutralization by antibodies induced following previous infections with another variant [55]. Thus, cross-protection is a critical issue in vaccine efficacy [45,56]. In this regard, HA-RBD vaccination led to the induction of nAbs that proved sufficient to prevent the manifestation of any pathological symptom and ensured full survival upon challenge with the heterologous Delta strain, being comparable to the clinically approved vaccine Nuvaxovid. Additionally, mice re-challenged with the Omicron variant displayed only negligible traces of viral presence in the nasal turbinates when compared to control mice that have an important localization of virus in the upper airways [57], even in the presence of apparently low titres of nAbs. Since the reduced neutralization activity against the Omicron variant is likely associated with mutations occurring in the Spike protein [58,59], this result could be attributed to the action of T-cell response [60] as suggested by the remarkable presence of antibody of the IgG2c subclass. Another mechanism that could properly justify the success of HA-RBD against Omicron re-challenge, likely relies on the elicitation of the mucosal immunity as already implied by other studies [61,62]. Notwithstanding further studies are certainly required to investigate these aspects in detail, our results collectively confirm that the HA-RBD vaccine not only protected mice from the infection with the homologous Wuhan strain but also conferred cross-protective immunity against infection with Delta and Omicron variants of concern, a condition that represents an occurrence largely experienced during the pandemic [63].

Another critical point in the validation of a potential new vaccine is the ability to ensure long-term protection, an issue that proved to be a limit of mRNA vaccines [44]. In this regard, the maintenance of circulating long-term antigen-specific IgGs and the concurrent presence of LLPCs cells, which produce high-affinity somatically mutated antibodies in a continuous manner to maintain serum levels constant, are considered a fundamental requisite to achieve durable humoral immune response [64]. Data obtained with the prototype HA-RBD vaccine clearly confirmed previous evidence obtained with HA-OVA model and indicated that HA is able to stimulate a long-lasting humoral immune response. In accordance, nAbs elicited by HA-RBD not only persisted for almost the entire lifespan of vaccinated mice correlating with circulating RBD-specific IgGs, but were still sufficient to confer protection against a viral lethal challenge carried out more than 8 months after priming. The death of two out of the five mice correlated with the low amount of circulating antibodies and can be justified by the inability to achieve an effective antigen re-stimulation, a situation that likely reflects inter-individual differences in vaccine response as largely experienced in

humans during the pandemic [65,66].

5. Conclusion

On the whole, our data show that antigen protein conjugation to HA represents a vaccine platform with relevant implications for clinical application. Indeed, HA-RBD not only elicited a specific and durable immune response against SARS-CoV-2 without triggering inflammation at the site of injection, but also conferred long-term cross-protection from the development of COVID-19 disease driven by different variants.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anna Dalla Pietà: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Beatrice Genova:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alessandro Penna:** Methodology, Investigation. **Alessandro Sinigaglia:** Investigation. **Stefania Vogiatzis:** Investigation. **Luisa Barzon:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Matteo Pagliari:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Francesco Bonfante:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Filippo Torrigiani:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Tomasoni Sofia:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Ranieri Verin:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Anna Tosi:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Debora Carpanese:** Investigation. **Roberta Sommaggio:** Methodology, Investigation. **Vito Barbieri:** Investigation. **Silvia Dalla Santa:** Formal analysis. **Gaia Zuccolotto:** Resources. **Antonella Grigoletto:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Gianfranco Pasut:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Antonio Rosato:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

ADP, DC and AR are inventors on patent application n° PCT/IB2019/059122 submitted on 24 October 2019 related to "Hyaluronic acid as a natural adjuvant for protein and peptide-based vaccines". All other authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2025.113674>.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available upon request.

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